

WHAT IS THE TREATMENT, CAUSES AND PREVENTIVE MEASURES OF BUGS?

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Abstract. *Goiter (Goitre) is an enlargement of the thyroid gland. The disease is most common in iodine-deficient countries, but can also develop as a result of iodine overload due to excessive consumption of iodine supplements. In this article, we will explain in detail how to follow a healthy lifestyle.*

Keywords: *treatment of bullies, causes of development, etiology, classification of thyroid diseases.*

ЗОБ: ЛЕЧЕНИЕ, ПРИЧИНЫ И ПРОФИЛАКТИЧЕСКИЕ МЕРЫ

Аннотация. *Зоб (Зоб) представляет собой увеличение щитовидной железы. Заболевание наиболее распространено в йододефицитных странах, но может развиваться и в результате йодной перегрузки из-за чрезмерного потребления йодсодержащих добавок. В этой статье мы подробно объясним, как вести здоровый образ жизни.*

Ключевые слова: *лечение буллингов, причины развития, этиология, классификация заболеваний щитовидной железы.*

INTRODUCTION

According to a WHO study, the incidence of goiter among children has increased by 6% in the last 10 years, which accounts for a quarter of all endocrine diseases in children. Such high indicators are due to poor nutrition, as well as unfavorable environmental conditions. In 30% of cases, the bull is diagnosed after the age of 14.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Goitre (Goiter) - enlargement of the thyroid gland. The disease is most common in iodine-deficient countries, but can also develop as a result of iodine overload due to excessive consumption of iodine supplements. It occurs 5 times more often in women than in men. Nodules are numerous fibrous scars formed in the thyroid tissue.

The most common form of this disease in the world is an endemic disease. This is due to iodine deficiency. In countries where iodized salt is used, Hashimoto's rash is usually formed, its alternative name is autoimmune thyroiditis.

Other reasons can be divided into two conditional groups:

1. HYPOTHYROIDISM:

- Genetic disorders of endocrine gland hormone processing (for example, cretinism);
- Consumption of stromogenic products;
- Side effects after taking the drug.

Symptoms of hypothyroidism include hair loss, dry and flaky skin, brittle nails, thinning eyebrows, loss of appetite, and weight gain. In diseases of the thyroid gland, speech slows down, memory deteriorates, there is almost constant drowsiness, and the menstrual cycle is disturbed. In this case, the presence of all these signs may not be observed, there are 2-3 signs, but they are more obvious.

2. HYPERTHYROIDISM:

- A diffuse type of toxic rash called Graves' disease;
- Thyroiditis (active inflammatory processes);
- Thyroid oncology.

Hyperthyroidism is an increase in thyroid hormones. Insomnia, general weakness, restlessness, increased heart rate, and excessive sweating are observed in this disease. A patient with this disease may have a good appetite, but begin to lose weight. In addition, there is high blood pressure, swelling of the eyes, tremors in the hands.

Classification of thyroid diseases

Thyroid diseases can be classified according to different causes, the first of which is etiopathogenetic. It determines the factors and mechanisms of the formation of the disease. On this basis, there are endemic (specific to a certain area) and sporadic bulls. The former produces endemic bulls in geographic regions, and the latter breeds bulls in all other countries.

RESULTS

According to their morphology, there are diffuse, nodular and mixed (diffuse-nodular) boils. By location:

- Default location;
- Partially behind the chest;
- a ring;
- Dystopyriv.

In addition, the disease also varies depending on the degree of enlargement of the gland. According to WHO (World Health Organization) classification, it can be divided into three types:

- Zero degree;
- First degree;
- Second level.

In the first stage, the gland does not enlarge, in the second stage it enlarges, but it is felt only by palpation, in the third stage - it is so enlarged that it is visible even to the naked eye.

Detailed classification by magnification O.V. According to Nikolaev, if not treated properly, the disease goes through the following stages:

- Primary - the thyroid gland is not palpable;
- The second is the thyroid gland;
- The third is a significant thickening of the neck;
- The fourth is a change in the shape of the neck;
- The fifth is a seriously enlarged goiter
- Location of the thyroid gland

Such forms as Bazedov's disease or hyperplasia have the following symptoms:

- A slight increase in body temperature for a long time;
- Weight loss;
- Swelling of the eyes (swelling of the eyes);
- Starve immediately;
- Excessive sleeplessness;
- Occasional discomfort;

- Progressive tremors in the hands.

Reasons for the development of bull (zob).

The factors that directly affect the formation of the bull should be considered in detail. The reason for this is that damage to the endocrine glands, as well as their causes, can be different.

As mentioned above, the main reason for the development of endemic toxic goiter is lack of iodine in the body. Its lack is explained by the fact that certain areas (settlements) do not have the necessary compounds. This leads to a decrease in the level of secretory activity of the gland.

In addition, a negative effect on the functioning of the thyroid gland is also associated with poor environmental performance. When external toxic compounds enter the human body, they slow down the endocrine system.

Endemic goiter can also occur as a result of relatively low consumption of iodine-containing products. We are talking about fish, fruit and milk.

In the case of Basedov's disease or diffuse toxic goiter, the gland is affected by specific antibodies. They are produced by the human body and are an integral part of the immune system against its own tissues. In this case, we will talk about the structure of the thyroid gland.

Taking into account the most important factors in the development of nodular warts, the following should be distinguished.

- Endocrine gland adenoma;
- Tumors of oncological origin.

As a result of such injuries, progressive disorders of cell division and differentiation occur. It can have radioactive effects, dangerous toxic substances and genetic properties.

- Anatomy of the thyroid gland
- Anatomy of the thyroid gland
- CHILDREN'S DISEASE

Special attention should be paid to gout in children, because it is the most common iodine deficiency disease. In most cases, children develop a diffuse form of the disease.

Symptoms of the disease are obvious in children. In addition, only in children, the disease can cause complications such as the development of a specific endemic cretinism. This form is accompanied by a delay in not only intellectual but also physical development and central nervous system disorders.

Diagnosis of thyroid disease

Blood and urine laboratory tests are used to detect goiter. The blood of a person with any clinical signs of the disease is checked for the ratio of hormones such as TTG, T3, T4 and thyroglobulin. The diagnosis is usually associated with an imbalance of thyroid hormones and an increase in thyroglobulin in those with this type of disease. At the same time, the excretion of iodine in the urine decreases.

An instrumental method of diagnosing goitre is ultrasound examination (UTT, UZI). With its help, it is possible to distinguish the form of the disease, for example, diffuse or nodular goiter. The functional state of the endocrine gland is evaluated using radioisotope scanning.

Experts recommend biopsy of the gland as an additional method of examination in the nodular form of endemic goitre. This allows to determine the nature of the disease. It can be good or bad quality.

If a thyroid gland is detected on palpation, the following mandatory tests should be performed to make an accurate diagnosis and determine the etiology and stage of the disease:

Take a blood test to determine the ratio and level of hormones (it is recommended to repeat the test within two to three months from the start of treatment);

- Electrocardiogram (ECG);
- Time-tested reflexes;
- UT examination of the thyroid gland.
- UT examination in the diagnosis of goiter

TESTS FOR INDEPENDENT DETERMINATION OF THE LEVEL OF IODINE IN THE ORGANIZATION

The three most accurate and easy tests to determine the ratio of iodine in the body:

- Test 1. This is done as follows: you need to take a simple 3 or 5% iodine solution. It should be used to draw bars on the body, and if possible, this should be done in the evening after physical activity. Pay special attention to the abdomen and waist. When the iodine is completely dry, lie down and sleep. Thus, if at least half of the cells are "absorbed" in the morning, then the amount of iodine in the body is insufficient. If these lines are clearly visible for more than 12 hours, especially for 24 hours, then this indicates an excess of iodine in the body, which must be dealt with.

- 2 - test. The second test consists of the following steps: dip a cotton swab in an alcohol solution of iodine. After that, grid-shaped lines are drawn on any part of the body (except the thyroid gland). The next day, the place will be carefully inspected. If there are no traces of iodine, then the body needs it, but if these lines remain, then there is no deficiency.

- Test 3. Finally, the third and very specific test. To perform this test, three strips of iodine are applied to the skin of the forearm before going to bed. Do this in sequence: first a thin line, then a little thicker, and the third is the thickest. If the first line disappears in the early morning, then the iodine level is normal. If you do not see the first two lines, pay attention to your health. In the same way, if there is no line left, we can talk about iodine deficiency.

DISCUSSION

Methods of treatment of bulls

Early detection of symptoms is the key to successful treatment, which helps to fight the disease as soon as possible. Thus, if an enlarged thyroid gland is felt, an endocrinologist should be consulted. It is important to consult an endocrinologist, because other specialists can simply eliminate the symptoms of fatigue.

Thyrostatic drugs, radioactive iodine and surgery are used to treat a poisonous insect. Currently, imidazole derivatives (merkazolyl, carbimazole and methimazole) are widely used. From thiouracil products, propylthiouracil is used. Mercazolil inhibits the phase of thyroid hormones produced by MIT and DIT, as well as the iodination of tyrosine residues by thyroglobulins.

Thyroid hypofunction is also corrected by normalizing hormone levels. However, in hyperfunction, everything is more complicated. For example, if there is a risk of tumors of any origin, it will be necessary to remove the gland surgically. This practice changes the condition to hypothyroidism. In turn, treatment of this condition is easier and more convenient thanks to hormone therapy.

In more severe forms of hypofunction of the endocrine glands, a person may fall into a coma. Hyperfunction can lead to fatal consequences (death) as a result of a toxic crisis. In this regard, it is necessary to follow a strict diet and maintain the necessary ratio of iodine in the body. At the same time, you should conduct regular examinations and tests for the amount of iodine. It has been repeatedly emphasized that iodine deficiency and excess lead to disease.

Surgery and radioactive iodine

Surgery on the thyroid gland is very difficult because it involves a lot of blood vessels. This makes the operation more problematic. However, in some cases there is no choice but to operate, so cataract surgery is one of the most commonly used treatment methods.

Surgery removes large nodules or potentially dangerous parts of the gland under anesthesia. In the most complicated and neglected cases, it may be necessary to remove part or the entire thyroid gland. However, even when removing one or more nodes, there is a need for medication recovery.

Prevention of BULLS

Prevention of bullfighting can be done in three ways - mass, group and individual. The most effective measure is the first, which is done by adding a small amount of iodine to the products that everyone eats. We are talking about iodized salt.

COCLUSIONS

Many believe that they can meet their daily iodine needs by eating certain foods that contain iodine. However, this is not 100% true, as significant changes in diet are required to overcome the existing deficiency. Second, such changes can be costly. Also, memory usage should be a fixed amount. In any case, any change: from an increase to a deficiency, causes problems with the endocrine glands and health in general.

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